

Lightweight artificial aggregates from ornamental rock cutting sludge and aggregate washing sludge: raw material for sustainable construction and agriculture

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lightweight aggregates
Waste recycling
Sustainable construction
Sustainable agriculture
Mixture experiments
Design experiments

ABSTRACT

Lightweight aggregates (LWAs) were produced exclusively from waste-derived raw materials: aggregate washing sludge, granite cutting sludge, slate cutting sludge and cork dust. The composition and number of mixtures were designed following a protocol based on Mixture Experiments-Design of Experiments (ME-DOE). The produced materials were technologically characterized by determining the bloating index (BI), oven-dry density (ρ_{rd}), water absorption (WA_{24}), strength (S), and additional parameters such as porosity and open porosity volume per specimen. Statistical models developed for BI , ρ_{rd} , WA_{24} and S provided a more accurate understanding of the behavior of the mixture components and their synergistic effects, using response surface and effect plots. A cork dust content of approximately 1.5 % was established as the optimal value for maximizing BI and WA_{24} , while minimizing ρ_{rd} . The resulting models are statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) and showed high coefficients of determination (R^2 : 0.80–0.94), suggesting a strong correlation with the experimental data. Moreover, predictive models were developed for the operational variables temperature (T) and optimum water content for extrusion (W_{op}) as a function of the mixture composition, supporting process manufacturing. Finally, the use of these residues in the production of LWAs has environmental benefits, with GWP reductions of between 13 and 36 % for SCS and 56–78 % for GCS compared to expanded clay lightweight aggregates, resulting in products with a lower environmental footprint.

1. Introduction

Pollution is one of the main challenges significantly impacting our planet's natural resources and climate change (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2023). One of the most important anthropogenic sources of environmental pollution are urban areas and the buildings within them. In this regard, the United Nations Environment Programme states that 'buildings are a very important part of environmental degradation', since they consume large amounts of natural resources during construction and are responsible for 40 % of greenhouse gas emissions and for 35 % of total waste generation in the EU (United

Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], s.f.). Given this context, there is a clear need to adopt environmentally friendly construction techniques and materials. An evolution towards sustainable construction practices is necessary.

Aggregates are among the most widely used materials with the highest environmental impact in the construction industry. In Spain, aggregates consumption for construction reached 143.6 million tones (Mt) in 2022, representing 75.6 % of the total market. Of this, 137.4 Mt were natural aggregates, 4.5 Mt recycled aggregates and 1.7 Mt artificial aggregates (ANEFA, s.f.). Based on the EU average per capita (5.7 Mt/year), Spain should consume approximately 270 Mt for

This article is part of a special issue entitled: WWEM-GEET-GC-2024 published in Environmental Research.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2025.122321>

Received 27 February 2025; Received in revised form 4 July 2025; Accepted 7 July 2025

Available online 8 July 2025

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construction, nearly double the 2022 value, indicating a clear trend of increasing demand. A study published by Zhong et al. (2022) projects a 45 % global increase in sand demand by 2060. This surge is expected to result in sand shortages, encouraging the use of alternative materials such as gravel, slag, aggregates, demolition waste and crushed concrete mixed with cement. Such growth in aggregate demand will place further pressure on natural aggregate reserves, underscoring the need for alternative options such as artificial aggregates made entirely from waste, which are suitable for use in lightweight concrete, green roofs and other sustainable construction solutions (Khan et al., 2024; Koviessen et al., 2023; Tazi et al., 2021).

Moreover, climate change also poses major challenges to agricultural systems, negatively affecting crop yields and farmer livelihoods (Cohn et al., 2017). The integration of circular economy principles into agriculture, known as circular farming, promotes sustainable agricultural practices that enhance sustainable food production, improve resource use and reduce waste. These systems are resilient, contribute to climate change mitigation and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, while also delivering economic benefits for farmers (Hilmi et al., 2024; Rakotovo et al., 2021; Velasco-Muñoz et al., 2021; Zeweld et al., 2018).

In this context, agricultural practices are increasingly focused on closing nutrients loops, such as feeding food waste to livestock or using crop residues as fertilizers (Hill et al., 2023; Payne and Kwofie, 2024). Another promising application of circular economy principles is the use of artificial lightweight aggregates as a hydroponic growing medium, as they are lightweight, highly porous and capable of retaining water while allowing root aeration. Such characteristics make them equally valuable for gardening, floriculture and green roof applications (Barbi et al., 2020; Martínez-García et al., 2021; Ronga et al., 2020; Stempkowska and Gawenda, 2024).

Both activities are closely related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the United Nations (United Nations, s.f.). Thus, construction to SDG 9 (Industry, innovation and infrastructure) and SDG 11 (Sustainable cities and communities), while also impacting SDG3 (Health and well-being of society, SDG6 (Clean water and sanitation), SDG7 (Affordable and clean energy), SDG8 (Decent work and economic growth), SDG12 (Responsible production and consumption) and SDG13 (Climate action) (Fleming et al., 2017; Inova Labs, s.f.; Maher and Buhmann, 2019). Moreover, sustainable agriculture integrates economic development, social equity and environmental protection, and thus the transformation towards agri-food systems contributes to all 17 SDGs and is essential for achieving them (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, s.f.).

The term *natural stone* or *ornamental rock* refers to rocks that, after extraction and processing, keep their composition, texture and physico-chemical properties, so they are suitable for high-value uses such as construction materials (paving, cladding, masonry, roofing, etc.), ornamental elements, funerary art, sculpture and other artistic applications. Globally, these rocks are classified into three main types: granites, marbles and slates (Centro de Estudios y Experimentación de Obras Públicas [CEDEX], 2015). In 2021, global ornamental rock production reached 155,000 kilotonnes, with China and India leading at 34 % and 18 % of total production, respectively. Spain ranked eighth, accounting for 3 % of global output (Instituto Geológico y Minero de España [IGME], 2023).

During the ornamental stone manufacturing process (cutting and polishing), two types of inert waste are generated: offcuts and sludge, the latter composed of cooling water from the looms and grains of the processed rock. This sludge contains not only fine particles from the source rock, but also additives used during processing (such as lime and shot) and particles resulting from the wear of the cutting and polishing equipment. The sludges are thickened by primary decantation using flocculants, recovering the clarified water and reused in the process. The thickened sludge is either stored in evaporation ponds or subjected to a dewatering process using high-performance filter presses. After filtration, the solid-to-liquid ratio reaches approximately 80/20. Finally,

filtered sludge is either stockpiled in large quantities, resulting in significant environmental and economic impact and potentially becoming a source of pollution, or, at best, is sent to landfills, which entails disposal costs (CEDEX, 2015; Epiroc, s.f.; Medina et al., 2020). These inert sludges are classified in the European Waste Catalogue under code 01 04 13 'waste from cutting and sawing of stone other than those mentioned in 01 04 07' (European Commission, 2000).

In Spain, slate remains the most economically significant and highly produced ornamental rock due to its recognized international quality, accounting for approximately 60 % of the total production value. It is followed by granite and ornamental limestone (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico [MITECO], 2024). In 2023, slate and granite production amounted to 1028 kt and 1465 kt, respectively (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico [MITECO], 2022), of which approximately 20–30 % is expected to become waste sludge during the cutting and polishing processes (Medina et al., 2017).

Numerous authors have explored the valorization of slate cutting sludge (SCS) and granite cutting sludge (GCS), mainly in the construction sector. The potential use has been investigated in porous and traditional ceramics (Acchar et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2025; Sadek et al., 2021), mortars (Lozano-Lunar et al., 2020; Mármol et al., 2010), concrete (Agrawal et al., 2022; Mashaly et al., 2018; Surra et al., 2023) and ceramic tiles (Torres et al., 2004). Other studies have focused on their application in geopolymer production (Carrillo Beltrán et al., 2024; Carrillo Beltrán et al., 2025; Picazo Camilo et al., 2025), as fillers in bituminous mixtures (Akbulut et al., 2012), and in other materials such as glass-ceramics (Lu et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2024a,b) or ceramic foams (Mu et al., 2024). However, to date, no references have been found on the use of these residues in the production of artificial lightweight aggregates (LWAs).

On the other hand, one of the operations involved in the conditioning and classification of natural aggregates is the washing of both raw and processed materials, which generates a waste known as aggregate washing sludge (AWS). This process poses several environmental challenges, such as high-water consumption, the generation of turbid water with a high content of suspended solids, visual impact and the occupation of large land areas (Bilici et al., 2023). The aggregate washing process is carried out, following the crushing and granulometric classification of the material, to separate the ultrafine particles such as clays and silts from the rest of the coarser granulometric fractions. Subsequently, the solid material is separated from the liquid in several stages ultimately producing a sludge. The method that has traditionally been used for the separation of the solid fraction from the liquid fraction is the open-air dewatering settling basin (Blanco, 2004; González-Corrochano et al., 2009). Sludge is a fine residue consisting of particles of approximately 80 µm in size, and constitutes between 5 % and 15 % of the initial product (Generalitat de Catalunya, s.f.). Sludge has normally been considered a reject material and has traditionally been stored in holes on the farm itself. However, decantation and filtration techniques are increasingly being used to separate the solid from the liquid fraction (Clearwater Industries, s.f.; Flottweg, 2025). Currently, alternative applications for this sludge are being developed, including its use as an agricultural product (with the aim of remineralising and reducing the stony nature of the soil), in the ceramics industry (manufacture of glass, ceramics, sandstone and porcelain), in the chemical industry (manufacture of cement and melting of metals) and in the construction sector (Al-Otaibi et al., 2020; Bilici et al., 2023; Blanco, 2004; Generalitat de Catalunya, s.f.; Klosek-Wawrzyn and Bugaj, 2018; Li et al., 2024; Miyano et al., 2024; Terrones-Saeta et al., 2024).

In recent years, there has been great interest in the scientific community in the development of artificial lightweight aggregates (LWAs) obtained partially or entirely from different types of waste. In this regard, several reviews have been published that compile and classify a large number of studies in this field according to different criteria (Dondi et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2022; Kwek and Awang, 2021; Nadesan and Joy,

2022; Wang and Dong, 2024). These reviews highlight the role of organic waste in the expansion process of the aggregates, as well as in porosity generation (Aguir et al., 2024; Cobo-Ceacero et al., 2023; Lim et al., 2023). This growing interest aligns with the expected increase in the demand for this product in the coming years, emphasizing the urgent need to develop scalable processes for producing aggregates, particularly lightweight ones. In this way, it will be possible to meet the needs of high-demand sectors such as construction, agriculture and gardening, while simultaneously reducing environmental pressure through the use of waste-derived raw materials.

This study focuses on the production of artificial lightweight aggregates (LWAs) exclusively from waste derived from the ornamental Stone industry (SCS and GCS) and aggregates sector (AWS), together with an organic residue: cork dust (CD) generated during the manufacturing of cork stoppers. To this end, a statistical protocol was implemented to define the formulations of the initial mixtures and to subsequently analyze the characterization results of the LWAs obtained using the Mixture Experiments - Design of Experiments (ME-DOE) (Cornell, 2002), with the support of R software (version 4.4.1) and Design Expert (version 12). The methodology applied has enabled the optimisation of the initial compositions to achieve the desired values for the technological properties under study: maximum values for mechanical strength (S), bloating index (BI) and water absorption after 24 h (WA_{24}), and a minimum value for oven-dry density (ρ_{rd}). Finally, depending on the technological characteristics of the materials produced, these LWAs may be used in the construction sector for applications such as lightweight concrete or green roofs, in agricultural sector for horticulture and hydroponics, or in landscaping, floriculture and gardening.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. RAW materials and characterisation

Four different waste materials have been used in this research: three of mineral origin (sludge from the aggregate washing process (AWS), granite cutting and polishing sludge (GCS) and slate cutting and polishing sludge (SCS)), and one of organic waste (cork dust (CD)) generated in the bottle stopper manufacturing process. Table 1 shows information on the companies which supply the waste.

Once the residues were received, they were dried in an oven at $105^\circ \pm 5^\circ \text{C}$, except for the CD, which was already dry upon delivery. The particle size of all the materials was suitable, so grinding was not required in any case. Table 2 shows the characterization tests performed on the residues.

Additionally, given its organic nature, the higher calorific value (HCV) and lower calorific value (LCV) of the CD was determined according to ISO 18125:2017.

Table 1
Waste supply companies.

Waste	Abbreviation	Company	Localisation	Web address
Granite cutting sludge	GCS	BLOKDEGAL	Porriño (Pontevedra)	http://www.blokdegal.com/es/canteras/
Slate cutting sludge	SCS	NATURPIEDRA	Bernardos (Segovia)	https://naturpiedra.com/es/
Aggregate washing sludge	AWS	Hermanos Moral Cantera Anoreta S.L	Villanueva de la Reina (Jaén)	https://aridoshermanos.com/
Cork dust	CD	EUROTAPÓN NÚÑEZ S.L.	San Vicente de Alcántara (Badajoz)	https://eurotapon-nunez.com/es/

Table 2

Analytical tests and working conditions of the equipment used for waste characterization.

Characterisation test	Equipment and operatin conditions
Chemical composition	Was carried out by X-ray fluorescence, using a Thermo ARL ADVANT ^{XP} Sequential XRF, performing the test in He atmosphere
Loss-on-ignition (LOI)	Was determined by calcining the samples at 1050°C for 2 h in a muffle.
Particle size distribution	Was obtained by laser diffraction with a Coulter [®] LS [™] 230
Mineralogy	Was studied by X-Ray Diffraction using a PANalytical [®] X'Pert Pro MRD diffractometer, the test condition was: 45 kV, 40 mA, CuK α radiation and a system of slits (soller – mask – divergence – antiscatter) of 0.04 rad–10 mm – $1/8^\circ$ ($1/16^\circ$ for OA) – $1/2^\circ$ ($1/4^\circ$ for OA) with an Xacute;celerator detector
Simultaneous Differential Thermal Analysis-Thermogravimetric Analysis (DTA-TG)	Was determinate using a SETARAM [®] equipment, Air atmosphere. Maximum temperature: 1200°C ; ramp: $10^\circ \text{C}/\text{min}$; air flow rate: 30 ml/min; Pt melting pot

Table 3

Composition of the mixtures studied.

Mix	GCS-CD-AWS			SCS-CD-AWS		
	Components, %			Components, %		
	GCS	CD	AWS	SCS	CD	AWS
M1	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
M2	0.00	1.50	98.50	0.00	1.50	98.50
M3	0.00	3.00	97.00	0.00	3.00	97.00
M4	17.50	0.75	81.75	20.00	0.75	79.25
M5	17.50	2.25	80.25	20.00	2.25	77.75
M6	35.00	0.00	65.00	40.00	0.00	60.00
M7	35.00	1.50	63.50	40.00	1.50	58.50
M8	35.00	3.00	62.00	40.00	3.00	57.00
M9	52.50	0.75	46.75	60.00	0.75	39.25
M10	52.50	2.25	45.25	60.00	2.25	37.75
M11	70.00	0.00	30.00	80.00	0.00	20.00
M12	70.00	1.50	28.50	80.00	1.50	18.50
M13	70.00	3.00	27.00	80.00	3.00	17.00

2.2. LWAs manufacturing and optimisation statistical protocol

Traditionally, the methods used to produce lightweight aggregates from multicomponent mixtures required extensive experimental work due to the need to test a large number of mixtures at different sintering temperatures (Mi et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2021; Mañosa et al., 2021; Pei et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2023). A new alternative has emerged with the use of statistical methods in mixture design (Moreno-Maroto et al., 2023a).

This study adopted a protocol based on Mixture Experiments-Design of Experiments (ME-DOE) using the statistical software R and Design Expert has been adopted for the selection of the mixtures to be tested and the subsequent analysis of the results obtained through four properties of the manufactured LWAs: bloating index (BI), oven-dry density (ρ_{rd}), water absorption during 24 h (WA_{24}) and crushing strength (S). The sequence of the protocol, according to Moreno-Maroto et al., 2023a, is shown in Fig. 1.

2.2.1. Sample planning

ME-DOE is a statistical approach developed to study the effect of component proportions on the properties of a mixture. It systematically explores the constrained mixture space to identify optimal formulations

Fig. 1. Experimental protocol based on *Mixture Experiments - Design of Experiments*.

and model the interactions among components. ME-DOE uses regression models to determine the effect of the components of a mixture on LWA properties (Cornell, 2002; Wie et al., 2024). In this area, linear regression models are often too restrictive and do not adequately reflect the component effects, so higher-order polynomial models such as quadratic, special cubic and cubic models are typically used (Lawson, 2015). Depending on the number of coefficients in the model used, it is necessary to consider a minimum number of mixtures to ensure they can be accurately estimated.

The ME-DOE proposed in the present research works with three final components for each set of experiments: AWS, a basic component included in all mixtures to provide plasticity, ornamental stone cutting sludge (GCS or SCS) and an organic waste additive (CD) to promote expansion.

Since GCS and SCS lack plasticity, it was necessary to add AWS, a residue with high plasticity (PI 51.0; Table 6) due to its high phyllosilicate content (Table 5), in order to form and pelletise the samples. This requirement determined that the maximum limits established for GCS and SCS in mixtures were 70 % and 80 %, respectively. For the organic additive, the upper limit has been set at 3 % in accordance with published work indicating that higher percentages of organic matter can restrict the expansion process in LWAs (Cobo-Ceacero et al., 2023). The third component, AWS, has been included in the mixtures in amounts up to 100 %, with a minimum of 27 % for GCS and 17 % for SCS. These limits for the three components result in a constrained mixture design (Cornell, 2002). Thus, an extreme vertices design of the experimental region augmented with edge centroids and interior points was used (Lawson, 2015), resulting in 13 formulations necessary to estimate the best-fit model for each LWAs property (Table 3). Mixtures M1, M6 and M11 contain only inorganic residues, allowing the effect of the additive on expansion capacity to be assessed.

2.2.2. LWAs manufacturing

The Atterberg liquid limit and plastic limit (LL and PL; ISO 17892-12, 2018) and the plasticity index ($PI = LL - PL$) were determined for all the mixtures. From these values, the optimum water content (W_{op}) was calculated as $W_{op} = 1.234 \times PI$ (Moreno-Maroto and Alonso-Azcárate, 2017). Based on this parameter, the wet mixtures were prepared and kept under these conditions for 24 h. Cylindrical samples were then extruded using a Nannetti® pneumatic extruder, cut and manually shaped into spheres. The resulting pellets were dried first at room temperature for 24 h and then in an oven at 105 ± 5 °C for another 24 h. The shaped pellets were subsequently thermally processed in a Nannetti® TOR-R 120-14 rotary tubular kiln, following this cycle: 2 min preheating followed by 4 min in the central part of the furnace at the maximum temperature, set as the highest temperature that allows proper firing of the LWAs without causing adhesion between them or with the furnace walls (Wie et al., 2020a; Wie et al., 2020b).

2.2.3. Determination of the technological properties of the LWAs

A complete characterisation of each of the different types of LWAs obtained was carried out based on the physical and mechanical

properties listed in Table 4. The loss on ignition (LOI) during the firing phase (LOI_{firing}) was calculated from the weight loss of 25 aggregates before and after the heating process in the rotary kiln. The bloating index (BI) was determined from the volume change of 25 aggregates before and after firing. The loose bulk density (ρ_b) was measured according to EN-1097-3 (1998) by weighing the aggregates in a container of known volume. The oven dry density (ρ_{rd}), apparent density (ρ_a) and water absorption after 24 h (WA_{24}) were measured using a water pycnometer according to EN-1097-6 (2022) and its Annex C.

The total porosity (P_T), open porosity (P_O) and closed porosity (P_C) values were calculated using Eqs. (1)–(3), respectively:

$$P_T = (1 - (\rho_{rd} / \rho_{solid})) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$P_O = (1 - (\rho_{rd} / \rho_a)) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$P_C = P_T - P_O \quad (3)$$

where:

ρ_{solid} is 2.6 g/cm³, this value represents the density of the solid phase of a conventional LWA (Akers et al., 2003).

The open porosity volume per specimen (V_{PO}) expressed in mm³, according to Moreno Maroto et al., 2023b, has been determined from the following equation:

$$V_{PO} = 4 / 3 \left[\pi(\emptyset/2)^3 \right] \times (P_O / 100) \quad (4)$$

where:

\emptyset is the diameter of the aggregate shown in Table 7 and P_O is the open porosity value calculated in Eq. (2).

Mechanical strength (S) was measured according to Yashima et al. (1987) and Li et al. (2000) on 25 specimens by means of an individual crush test using a Nannetti®FM 96 pneumatic press. The microstructure of selected specimens was analysed using a FE-SEM microscope model TESCAN CLARA, equipped with an E-T detector. The operating conditions were 20 Kv and at a working distance (WD) of 20 mm. Finally, the

Table 4
LWAs characterisation tests.

Property	Abbreviation	Comments
LOI during firing	LOI_{firing}	Weight loss before and after firing
Bloating index	BI	Change in diameter before and after firing
Loose bulk density	ρ_b	UNE-EN 1097-3, 1999
Apparent density	ρ_a	UNE-EN 1097-6, 2014
Oven-dry density	ρ_{rd}	UNE-EN 1097-6, 2014
Water absorption for 24 h	WA_{24}	UNE-EN 1097-6, 2014
Total, open and closed porosity	P_T ; P_O ; P_C	de Santiago Buey and García, 2008; Bernhardt et al. (2013)
Open porosity volumen per specimen	V_{PO}	Moreno Maroto et al. (2023b)
Mechanical strength	S	Yashima et al., 1987; Li et al., 2000

Table 5
Main characteristics of the wastes studied in this investigation.

Waste name	Chemical composition, oxides (%)										Mineralogy	
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃ ^a	Na ₂ O ^b	K ₂ O ^a	MgO ^b	CaO ^b	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	LOI ^b (%)	Major	Minor
GCS	69.4	12.7	4.1	3.0	4.4	1.6	3.6	0.4	0.1	0.6	Quartz, Plagioclase	Feldspar, Moscovite
SCS	63.2	15.5	7.5	2.1	3.7	2.4	1.2	0.9	0.1	3.2	Quartz Moscovite Chlorite	Feldspar Plagioclase
AWS	56.7	20.7	9.0	0.5	3.1	1.6	1.3	0.7	0.4	5.8	Quartz Illite Chlorite	Feldspar
CD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0	-	-

^a Fluxing oxides.

^b Loss of ignition.

Table 6
Plasticity parameters and optimum water content (*W_{op}*) of samples.

C1	LL	PL	PI	W _{op}	C2	LL	PL	PI	W _{op}
1-GCS-CD	74.6	26.3	48.3	32.5	1-SCS-CD	76.5	25.5	51.0	31.5
2-GCS-CD	73.4	27.3	46.1	33.6	2-SCS-CD	73.4	26.7	46.7	33.0
3-GCS-CD	71.8	28.2	43.6	34.8	3-SCS-CD	73.6	27.3	46.3	33.7
4-GCS-CD	66.0	23.9	42.1	29.5	4-SCS-CD	62.4	24.1	38.3	29.7
5-GCS-CD	66.0	25.9	40.1	31.9	5-SCS-CD	61.9	25.5	36.4	31.5
6-GCS-CD	55.8	22.6	33.2	27.9	6-SCS-CD	52.5	23.8	28.7	29.3
7-GCS-CD	56.6	25.2	31.3	31.1	7-SCS-CD	53.3	26.6	26.8	32.8
8-GCS-CD	58.7	27.0	31.7	33.3	8-SCS-CD	56.1	27.1	29.0	33.4
9-GCS-CD	49.8	25.0	24.7	30.9	9-SCS-CD	46.1	26.2	19.9	32.3
10-GCS-CD	51.2	27.2	23.9	33.6	10-SCS-CD	47.5	27.9	19.7	34.4
11-GCS-CD	42.6	28.2	14.4	34.8	11-SCS-CD	40.3	27.4	12.9	33.9
12-GCS-CD	44.1	29.2	14.9	36.1	12-SCS-CD	41.1	29.4	11.7	36.3
13-GCS-CD	46.3	33.8	12.4	41.7	13-SCS-CD	43.4	34.3	9.1	42.3

Table 7
Properties of the LWAs sintered from the mixture containing GCS-DC and SCS-DC.

C1					Density, g/cm ³			Porosity, %					
	T, °C	Ø, mm	BI, %	LOI _{firing} , %	ρ _b	ρ _a	ρ _{rd}	WA ₂₄ , %	P _T	P _O	P _C	V _{PO} , mm ³	S, MPa
1-GCS-CD	1195	9.06	9.83	5.91	0.81	1.50	1.40	4.9	46.2	6.7	39.5	26.0	6.8
2-GCS-CD	1170	11.33	34.66	7.58	0.41	0.87	0.71	25.0	72.7	18.4	54.3	140.1	2.4
3-GCS-CD	1160	9.88	18.60	8.97	0.59	1.26	1.00	21.1	61.5	20.6	40.9	104.2	5.5
4-GCS-CD	1180	11.87	37.68	5.94	0.39	0.82	0.69	23.3	73.5	15.9	57.6	138.8	1.2
5-GCS-CD	1175	11.15	29.39	7.36	0.44	0.94	0.76	24.3	70.8	19.1	51.6	139.0	2.7
6-GCS-CD	1205	8.23	-3.69	3.94	1.20	2.06	2.05	0.3	21.2	0.5	20.7	1.4	17.5
7-GCS-CD	1185	12.12	41.05	5.66	0.35	0.83	0.62	39.4	76.2	25.3	50.9	235.9	1.4
8-GCS-CD	1180	10.79	23.84	7.42	0.49	1.04	0.85	21.5	67.3	18.3	49.0	120.2	3.6
9-GCS-CD	1190	11.54	31.68	4.05	0.42	0.86	0.77	13.0	70.4	10.5	59.9	84.2	1.0
10-GCS-CD	1195	11.12	27.21	5.73	0.42	1.04	0.76	34.9	70.8	26.9	43.8	193.8	1.6
11-GCS-CD	1215	7.96	-10.21	2.23	1.40	2.41	2.35	1.0	9.6	2.5	7.1	6.6	23.9
12-GCS-CD	1205	10.60	18.88	3.90	0.60	1.22	1.00	17.2	61.5	18.0	43.5	112.5	1.8
13-GCS-CD	1205	10.24	14.08	5.28	0.53	1.19	0.90	26.9	65.4	24.4	41.0	137.0	2.9

C2					Density, g/cm ³			Porosity, %					
	T, °C	Ø, mm	BI, %	LOI _{firing} , %	ρ _b	ρ _a	ρ _{rd}	WA ₂₄ , %	P _T	P _O	P _C	V _{PO} , mm ³	S, MPa
1-SCS-CD	1195	9.17	11.12	6.19	0.81	1.48	1.38	5.1	46.9	6.8	40.2	6.8	6.8
2-SCS-CD	1170	11.29	34.39	7.33	0.40	0.91	0.74	26.0	71.5	18.7	52.9	2.3	2.3
3-SCS-CD	1160	9.84	19.00	9.22	0.59	1.25	0.98	21.9	62.3	21.6	40.7	5.3	5.3
4-SCS-CD	1185	11.57	37.94	6.42	0.40	0.83	0.69	24.1	73.5	16.9	56.6	1.6	1.6
5-SCS-CD	1170	11.16	29.79	7.85	0.44	0.96	0.78	25.1	70.0	18.8	51.3	2.4	2.4
6-SCS-CD	1220	9.04	5.16	4.85	0.93	1.56	1.53	1.5	41.3	2.3	39.0	8.9	9.5
7-SCS-CD	1190	12.33	42.15	6.54	0.35	0.73	0.58	33.4	77.7	20.5	57.1	1.0	1.0
8-SCS-CD	1175	11.19	27.18	8.08	0.43	1.00	0.76	31.2	70.8	24.0	46.8	2.2	2.2
9-SCS-CD	1200	10.82	21.76	5.47	0.45	0.91	0.80	14.2	69.2	12.1	57.1	1.5	1.5
10-SCS-CD	1195	11.59	30.94	7.02	0.35	0.77	0.64	27.1	75.4	16.9	58.5	1.8	1.8
11-SCS-CD	1225	8.12	-10.14	3.96	1.32	2.17	2.16	0.3	16.9	0.5	16.5	19.8	19.8
12-SCS-CD	1210	11.40	27.1	5.70	0.42	0.85	0.77	11.8	70.4	9.4	61.0	1.5	1.5
13-SCS-CD	1200	11.31	27.58	6.99	0.42	0.87	0.75	18.0	71.2	13.8	57.4	1.3	1.3

UNE-EN 13650:2002 standard ‘Soil improvers and growing media. Extraction of soluble elements in aqua regia’ was used to determine whether the LWAs obtained meet the specifications set out in RD 865/2010 for their use as growing media.

2.2.4. Statistical modelling

The fourth stage of the proposed statistical protocol consists of the statistical analysis of the results obtained in the previous stage, for which the variables *BI*, *ρ_{rd}*, *WA₂₄* and *S* were selected as they are considered decisive in the final performance of the LWAs depending on

their intended application. The objective was to relate the results of these four technological properties to the mixture composition using R software, with the *mixexp* package (Lawson and Willden, 2016), and Design Expert.

To establish the statistical relationship between composition and property values, linear, quadratic, cubic and special cubic regression models were tested. Specifically, denoting the mixture components as A, B, and C (where A = GCS or SCS, B = CD and C = AWS), the models tested can be expressed as follows.

- Linear: Response = A + B + C
- Quadratic: Response = A + B + C + AB + AC + BC
- Quadratic: Response = A + B + C + AB + AC + BC
- Cubic: Response = A + B + C + AB + AC + BC + ABC + AB(A-B) + AC(A-C) + BC(B-C)

In each case, the most appropriate one was selected based on statistical criteria. Thus, a sequential F-test was employed to compare nested models and the more complex model was retained if it produced a p-value below the significance level. Furthermore, a model diagnosis was conducted to verify that the regression assumptions were met, in particular, the linearity, normality and homoscedasticity hypotheses. For this purpose, residual plots were analysed, applying the following statistical tests: RESET test for the linearity hypothesis, Shapiro-Wilk and Anderson-Darling test for the normality hypothesis, and the Breusch-Pagan test for the homoscedasticity hypothesis. If the diagnosis was not satisfactory, a Box-Cox transformation of the response variable was applied, and a new diagnosis was performed on the transformed model.

Once the model has been selected, the effect plots and response

surface plots were generated for each technological property, allowing the estimation of how their value evolves with changes in the mixture composition, providing a practical means of designing LWAs tailored to the specific performance requirements of their intended application.

In addition, the values of temperature and optimum water content (W_{op}) used in the manufacturing process of the LWAs were considered in order to develop models relating these variables to mixture composition, following a similar approach to the one used for the technological properties described above. This makes it possible to estimate the optimum temperature and water content required for the LWAs production in subsequent stages, such as validation, thus reducing the number of tests needed and streamlining the manufacturing process.

Finally, the aggregates obtained from GCS and SCS were compared to assess whether there are differences between them or whether either waste type can be used interchangeably in the production process.

2.2.5. Optimisation and validation

The last stage of Fig. 1 involves the optimisation and validation of the process. The optimal formulations were defined as those that maximise or minimise the value of a given technological property based on the selected statistical models. Specifically, the aim was to maximise $B1$, WA_{24} and S , and minimise ρ_{rd} .

The process concludes with the validation of the results. For this purpose, using the optimal temperatures and water contents (W_{op}) estimated from the corresponding models, LWAs with optimal performance across the four properties were produced. These experimental LWAs were then characterised and compared with the predicted values from the statistical models (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Protocol optimisation and validation stage.

2.3. Environmental assessment of LWAs

A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been carried out to evaluate the environmental advantages of fully utilising waste to manufacture these materials compared to traditional activities. LCA is widely adopted as a powerful tool for quantifying, evaluating, comparing and improving the environmental impact of products throughout their life cycle (UNE-EN ISO 14040, 2006; Anderson et al., 2019). Conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) allows for the optimisation of inputs (materials and energy) and the minimisation of outputs (waste and environmental impacts) once new materials have been developed and analysed from a technological standpoint.

To quantify the environmental impact of the different materials developed, the following were used: (i) data measured and processed empirically in experimental research carried out in the laboratory, such as the proportions of materials used, energy consumed and gases emitted in the sintering process; (ii) bibliographic data; and (iii) the Life Cycle Assessment software SIMAPRO 8.3.0.0 and its ECOINVENT v.3.2 database.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterisation of raw materials and green mix

Table 5 shows the characterisation of the wastes used in this research. As expected, due to their origin, the chemical composition of GCS and SCS shows high percentages of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 (69.4–63.2 % and 12.7–15.5 %, respectively) values comparable to those commonly found in clays (Galán-Arboledas et al., 2013) and a significant flux content ($\sum \text{Flux} = \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{CaO} + \text{MgO} + \text{FeO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), higher than 16 % in both cases. This chemical composition is consistent with their mineralogy, which is mainly composed of quartz and alkali feldspar phases. Regarding AWS, it shows a high percentage of $\text{FeO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (9.0 %) and a mineralogy rich in phyllosilicates, primarily illite and chlorite, consistent with the clay-based origin of this waste (Galán-Arboledas et al., 2013). On the other hand, the organic waste presents a LOI value of 100 %, which aligns with the results obtained for its gross calorific value (HCV) and net calorific value (LCV) of $30,661.06 \pm 311.99$ kJ/kg and $28,798.33 \pm 311.99$ kJ/kg, respectively. These values are of the same order of magnitude as those reported for other wastes of the same nature (Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía [IDAE], s.f.).

The three mineral wastes exhibit a particle size distribution of suitable origin (Fig. 3) with an average particle diameter (d_{50}) of less than 10 μm and a fraction $>63 \mu\text{m}$ below 1.5 % in all cases, which is advantageous for their use in industrial processes. The finest sample is GCS

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution of waste.

with an average size of 8.5 μm , although it also exhibits the highest sand content (1.34 %).

For all mixtures, the plasticity parameters LL, PL and PI have been determined (Table 6). It is worth noting that the minimum AWS content required to form workable mixtures is 27 % in the case of GCS-based samples and 17 % for those with SCS, as this residue is responsible for providing the necessary plasticity due to its high phyllosilicates content (Table 5). In both cases, it can be observed that the PI of the mixture decreases as the AWS content decreases. For GCS-based mixtures, the PI ranges from 48.3 for the mixture with the highest AWS content to 12.4 for the one with the lowest. For SCS-based mixtures, the variation is even greater, ranging from 51.0 to 9.1. As for the W_{op} values, they range between a minimum of 27.9 % for sample 6-GCS-CD and a maximum of 42.3 % for sample 13-SCS-CD.

3.2. Behaviour of LWAs during the sintering process

According to the data in Tables 7 and it can be observed that increasing the percentage of cork dust promotes decrease in the sintering temperature in both sets of tested mixtures. For example, in the first three samples of each series, increasing the CD content from 0 to 3 % results in a temperature reduction of 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (from 1195 to 1160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). In mixtures 6, 7 and 8 of both series, which have a fixed contents of 35 % GCS and 40 % SCS, respectively, the same trend is observed: a 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ reduction for GSC-CD mixtures, and up to 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for SCS-CD mixtures, despite these samples exhibits higher sintering temperatures than the initial ones. This increase is attributed to the greater proportion of GSC or SCS, which correlates with an increase in the sintering temperature. Thus, samples 11, 12 and 13, with the highest GCS and CSC contents (70 and 80 %, respectively), display the highest sintering temperatures observed in this study (1200–1225 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Nevertheless, even in these cases, the addition of organic residue results in a temperature reduction of up to 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the case of SCS-based samples. This increase in sintering temperature with higher contents of ornamental stone cutting waste may be due to the high quartz (SiO_2) content in these residues (Table 5), as quartz is a highly refractory compound. The lowest sintering temperature observed was 1160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponding to mixture 3, which contains solely of AWS and the highest proportion of cork dust (3 %).

Regarding mass loss during sintering, the highest values, as expected, were recorded in the mixtures with the highest organic waste content, for a fixed percentage of inorganic residue, which also corresponds to the lowest sintering temperature. Conversely, the lowest mass loss was recorded in sample 11 in both series (2.23 % for GCS and 3.96 % for SCS), while the highest losses were observed in sample 3, with values of 8.97 % for the GCS mixture and 9.22 % for the SCS mixture. These findings are consistent with those reported by other authors (Moreno-Maroto et al., 2019). The thermal transitions contributing to the observed mass losses, to varying degrees, are illustrated in the TG/DTA curves in Fig. 4 (Földvári, 2011).

Given the high likelihood of an oxygen-deficient atmosphere during the sintering of LWAs, the organic matter in the waste undergoes incomplete oxidation, generating reducing conditions within the aggregate. These conditions promote the transformation of Fe_2O_3 into FeO , a process facilitated by the significant Fe_2O_3 content in the waste (Table 5). This transformation results in the formation of a 'black core', a phenomenon well documented in the literature (Lee et al., 2019; Park et al., 2005). Fig. 5 illustrates the LWAs obtained in this study, clearly showing the formation of this characteristic core. The chemical reactions leading to the formation of the black core enhance the viscous behavior of the aggregate, effectively reducing the temperature at which expansion occurs. This explains the previously observed decrease of up to 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in sintering temperature with increasing CD content for a constant proportion of the other two components. An additional benefit of 'black core' formation is that it prevents adhesion between aggregates during sintering by creating a reduction gradient in Fe_2O_3 between the

Fig. 4. TG-DTA graphs in air for the components of the mixtures: (a) GCS; (b) SCS; (c) AWS; (d) CD.

- Endothermic dehydroxylation of chlorite, muscovite and illite occurs between 500–580 °C and 820–920 °C in SCS and AWS to form H₂O (Fig. 4b) and c)).
- Exothermic oxidation of organic matter preset in AWS and CD takes place approximately between 250 and 500 °C releasing CO₂ y/o CO y H₂O_(g) (Fig. 4c) and d)).

shell and the core, thus promoting the necessary separation (Wie et al., 2020a; Wie et al., 2020b).

3.3. Technological properties of the manufactured LWAs

Table 7 shows the variation in the four technological properties used to construct the regression models. Only three formulations (6-GCS-CD, 11-GCS-DC y 11-SCS-CD) of the 26 formulations produced fail to meet the requirement established by UNE-EN 13055-1 (2003) for lightweight aggregates ($\rho_b < 1,20 \text{ g/cm}^3$ o $\rho_{rd} < 2,00 \text{ g/cm}^3$). The samples with the lowest ρ_{rd} values were 7-GSC-CD and 7-SCS-CD, 0.62 and 0.58 g/cm³ respectively, and both are characterised by having a GCS or SCS contents equal to half the maximum residue percentage used. These density values are comparable to those reported by Romero et al. (2024) who produced lightweight aggregates from the organic fraction of recycled alkaline batteries (Table 8). Moreover, formulations with the lowest ρ_{rd} values typically contain CD contents between 0.75 and 2.25 %, consistent with the findings of other researchers who have reported that small amounts of organic additives enhance the expansion process (Cobo-Ceacero et al., 2023). In general, the ρ_{rd} values obtained in this study are consistent with those reported by other authors using different types of waste materials (Table 8). Given the inverse relationship between density and the bloating index (BI), the 7-GSC-CD and 7-SCS-CD mixtures exhibit the highest BI values, at 41.05 % and 42.15 %, respectively. In contrast, those mixtures that fail to meet density standards display shrinkage effects, with negative BI values: 6-GCS-CD at -3,69 %, 11-GCS-CD at -10,21 %, 11-SCS-CD at -10,24 %. This shrinkage behaviour has also been reported by González-Corrochano et al. (2016) in lightweight aggregates produced from AWS and sewage sludge

(-10.87 %) and by Zhou et al. (2024a,b) in the valorization of sludge incineration waste (-14 %; -21 %).

The highest values of water absorption were observed in mixture 7 for both types of ornamental stone waste, 39.4 % for GCS-CD and 33.4 % for SCS-CD (Table 7). These values are of the same order as those reported by González-Corrochano et al. (2016), for lightweight aggregates sintered at 1275 °C from AWS (38.36 %). Notably, these mixtures also correspond to the highest BI values, confirming the positive correlation between expansion and water absorption. In contrast, the lowest values were recorded for mixtures 6-GSC-CD and 11-SCS-CD, at only 0.3 %, which are similar to those reported by Zhou et al. (2024a,b), Kockal and Ozturan (2019) (0.3 and 0.7, respectively; Table 8). Water absorption is directly related to lower density and increased porosity, as the presence of large or interconnected pores facilitates greater water penetration (Ji et al., 2023; Manikandan and Ramamurthy, 2012). The P_O values obtained for 7-GSC-CD and 7-SCS-CD (25,3 and 20,5 %, respectively) are within the ranges reported by other authors (Dondi et al., 2016) and are directly responsible for the WA_{24} values observed. However, since P_O is a relative value based on the total aggregate volume, a correction was introduced to account for the interconnected open pore volume actually available after expansion. The newly determined parameter V_{PO} (volume for open porosity per specimen), provides a more accurate representation of functional porosity. Fig. 6a illustrates the strong positive correlation between WA_{24} and V_{PO} , with correlation coefficients of 0.993 for GCS and r: 0.996 for SCS.

Mechanical strength is a key parameter in determining the potential commercial applications of LWAs. In this study, S values ranged from 1 to 23.9 MPa for the GCS-CD formulations and 1.0–19.8 MPa for SCS-CD, with the highest value corresponding to aggregates not classified as

Fig. 5. Exterior (shell) and interior (core) of the aggregate formulations manufactured in this research to test the statistical models.

Table 8
The comparison of physical and mechanical properties of LWAs with the literature.

Ref.	Mixture composition	Sintering temperature, °C	Sintering time, min	ρ_{rd} , g/cm ³	WA ₂₄ , %	S, MPa	BI, %
Ozkan et al., 2022	Washing aggregate sludge and ground granulated blast furnace slag	1150	15	1.65	22.8	10.0	
González-Corrochano et al., 2016	Washing aggregate sludge and sewage sludge	1175–1275	1–30	1.24–1.48	23.54–38.36	1.23–3.03	(–10.87)–(–1.94)
Li et al. (2024)	Sand washing slurry and red mud	1150	5			1.7	
Kockal and Ozturan, 2011	Fly ash, Bentonite and glass powder	1100–1200	60	1.51–1.93	0.7–18.4	5.1–23.1	
Huang et al. (2025)	Secondary aluminium dross (10–40 %)	1150–1250	10		5–35	0.5–3.3	
Zhou et al. (2024a,b)	Sludge incineration residue	1065–1115	10–40		0.3–2	7–20.5	(–14)–(–21)
Jaha et al. (2024)	Palygorskite-rich sediment and phosphate sludge	1100–1150	15	0.6–1.05	6–12	0.86–3.34	5.1–38.5
Romero et al. (2024)	Organic fraction from recycled alkaline batteries (5–15 %) and stoneware atomized paste	1200	15	0.67–0.75		1.34–1.39	96–128
Franus et al., 2015	Sewage sludge and clay	1100–1200	30	2.69–2.59	14.4–16.2	4.64–0.79	

lightweight. However, in general, the *S* values obtained in this research are slightly higher than those typically reported in scientific literature (Dondi et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2022; Kwek and Awang, 2021; Wang and Dong, 2024) and are comparable to, or even exceed, the mechanical

performance declared by some commercial LWAs manufacturers. For example, Abdelfattah et al. (2020) produced LWAs from clay and benonite with strengths ranging from 2.45 to 8.41 MPa, Li et al. (2024) reported a value of 1.7 MPa for aggregates made from sand washing

Fig. 6. Correlations between different variables: a) WA_{24} versus V_{PO} ; b) $S^{1/2}$ versus P_T .

slurry and red mud, and Zhou et al. (2024a,b) achieved 20.5 MPa using sludge incineration residue sintered at 1115 °C, all within or below the range obtained in the present study.

Table 9 presents the values of bulk density (ρ_b) and compressive strength (S) for commercial LWAs with particle size distributions similar to those used in this study (ARLITA, s.f.; Laterlite, 2021; NexClay, s.f.; Puma Group, 2024).

The comparison of the lightweight aggregates produced in this study (Table 7) with commercial aggregates (Table 9) reveals that most of the formulations developed have technological properties comparable to or even superior to those of commercial products. Specifically, formulations 4 and 7 of GCS-CD and 7 and 10 of SCS-CD exhibit loose bulk density (ρ_b) and mechanical strength (S) values similar to those of Arlita Leca M, Laterlite Expanded Clay and Puma Expanded Clay. This suggests their suitability for applications such as lightweight fillers and insulators, lightweight structural concrete, landscaping, green roofs and hanging gardens, as recommended for commercial products. Furthermore, the 3-GSC-CD and 3-SCS-CD formulations, with ρ_b and S values that align with Arlita Leca HS (ρ_b of 0.610 g/cm³ and S of 5 MPa), demonstrate the potential of these waste-based LWAs for civil engineering and structural concrete applications. Although the formulations in this study generally have slightly higher bulk densities than certain very lightweight commercial products such as NexClay with ρ_b of 0.217 g/cm³, they have the advantage of higher strength values ($S_{NexClay}$ 1.2 MPa). This is the case for formulations such as 2/5/13-GCS-CD and 2/5/8-SCS-CD with bulk densities in the range of 0.40–0.53 g/cm³ and mechanical strengths ranging from 2.2 to 2.9 MPa, between 80 and 140 % higher than that declared by NexClay. The combination of lightness and strength offered by the LWAs in these formulations makes them particularly interesting for use in lightweight structural concrete (da Silva Neto et al., 2025). This comparison highlights the potential for recycling ornamental stone waste to produce lightweight aggregates

Table 9
Technological properties and applications of commercial LWAs.

Commercial LWAs	Particle size, mm	ρ_b , g/cm ³	S, MPa	Applications
Arlita Leca L	10–20	0.275 ± 0.015	0.7	Light infill, roof insulation, gardening and
Arlita Leca M	4–12	0.330 ± 0.015	1.0	Precast, screeds and insulating concretes
Arlita Leca MS	2–11	0.465 ± 0.015	4.5	Compression layers, lightweight concretes
Arlita Leca HS	4–12	0.610 ± 0.015	5	Prestressed, civil engineering, structural concrete
Laterlite expanded clay	8–20	≈0.350	≥1.0	Flat and pitched roofs, floor and slab screeds, lightweight and insulating infill, insulation in contact with the ground, structural lightweight concrete, landscaping, green roofs and hanging gardens.
NexClay (3–8)	8–12,5	0.287 ± 0.015	1.8 ± 10 %	Fillings with good thermal and acoustic performance, geotechnical works, agriculture and
NexClay (8–16)	8–20	0.217 ± 0.015	1.2 ± 10 %	landscaping, drainage and insulation of slabs on the ground, retaining walls, planters and green roofs.
Puma Group: expanded clay	8–18	0.330	0.7	Slab screeds, insulating screeds on the ground, flat and pitched roofs, attics, garden filling, geotechnical applications, structural lightweight concrete, prefabricated

with competitive performance on the market.

Finally, Fig. 6b) illustrates the relationship between mechanical strength and total porosity, where the variable S was subjected to a square root transformed to satisfy the assumptions of linear regression. The figure shows the negative correlation between strength and porosity (r: 0.971 for GCS and r: 0.980 for SCS).

3.4. Statistical analysis of the results

Once the technological properties of the aggregates were determined, regression models were developed to best fit the parameters BI , ρ_{rd} , WA_{24} and S, following the methodology described in section 2.2.4. Diagnostic checks were carried out on the selected models and the appropriate variable transformations were applied where necessary to meet statistical assumptions. Although detailed diagnostics are not included here for brevity, they are provided in the supplementary material. Specifically, the logarithm transformation was applied to S, the square root to WA_{24} and the inverse of the square root to ρ_{rd} . In all cases, the quadratic model provided the best fit as shown in Table 10 where sequential p-values comparing models from the simplest (linear) to the most complex (cubic) are included. It should be noted that the more complex model with a p-value of less than 0.05 is preferable. Table 11 shows the estimated regression coefficients, the p-value of the overall F-test and both the coefficients of determination and predicted determination. All models were statistically significant (p-value <0.05) and exhibited high determination coefficients (R^2 : 0.80–0.94), indicating strong correlation with the observed data. Plots comparing the observed and model-predicted values for each property are available in the supplementary material.

The response surface and effect plots corresponding to the selected technological properties are shown in Figs. 7–10. In all cases, the response surface transition from deep blue to red, indicating increasing values of the evaluated property. The case of mechanical strength is

Table 10

Regression models for selected technological properties for GCS-CD and SCS-CD mix: sequential p-values for comparison of models.

Models	GCS-CD mix				SCS-CD mix			
	$\log S$	BI	$\sqrt{(WA_{24})}$	$1/\sqrt{(\rho_{rd})}$	$\log S$	BI	$\sqrt{(WA_{24})}$	$1/\sqrt{(\rho_{rd})}$
Linear	0.5045	0.2454	0.0203	0.1516	0.2063	0.1521	0.0086	0.1135
Quadratic	0.0130	0.0044	0.0111	0.0056	0.0034	0.0007	0.0042	0.0004
Special Cubic	0.8374	0.8889	0.7410	0.9837	0.4522	0.4984	0.5137	0.6951
Cubic	0.2160	0.1761	0.9109	0.2751	0.0504	0.3000	0.3053	0.3459

Table 11

Coefficients of the regression models for selected technological properties for GCS-CD and SCS-CD mix.

	GCS-CD mix				SCS-CD mix			
	BI	$1/\sqrt{(\rho_{rd})}$	$\sqrt{(WA_{24})}$	$\log S$	BI	$1/\sqrt{(\rho_{rd})}$	$\sqrt{(WA_{24})}$	$\log S$
CS ^a	-38.08	0.33	-0.62	4.02	-23.88	0.52	-1.36	3.44
CD	-103228.58	-1203.35	-9297.11	6900.77	-88195.56	-1112.38	-7256.76	5266.89
AWS	9.02	0.85	2.07	2.05	13.43	0.86	2.19	1.87
CD:CS ^a	107494.17	1258.56	9772.84	-7202.57	92430.58	1176.88	7637.31	-5529.86
AWS:CS ^a	59.65	0.65	1.46	-2.17	36.95	0.55	5.25	-2.00
CD:AWS	106696.41	1246.22	9665.09	-7112.05	91053.51	1161.93	7567.91	-5426.99
R ²	0.871	0.875	0.898	0.796	0.932	0.945	0.935	0.885
Predicted R ²	0.648	0.595	0.612	0.367	0.790	0.840	0.795	0.630
p-value	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.023	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.004

^a CS: granite or slate cutting sludge.

presented in Fig. 7a) and b) for GCS and SCS mixtures, respectively. These plots show that S generally increases with higher proportions of granite or slate sludge and lower cork dust content, while minimum strength occurs at intermediate CD levels ($\approx 1.5\%$). The effect plots further confirm that S is strongly influenced by CD, showing higher S values at the extremes, particularly at low CD contents. Higher levels of AWS, especially near the centroid (approximately 60%), are associated with a reduction in S .

Numerous authors have demonstrated a strong interrelationship between compressive strength and density, shape and surface characteristics of aggregates; the size and distribution of the pores; densification effects due to sintering; the bloating index; the mineral species present in the LWAs; the nature of newly formed phases; and the proportion of pore-forming agents. All of these factors significantly influence the physical, mechanical and microstructural properties of lightweight aggregates (Chang et al., 2007; Decler and Viaene, 1993; Fakhfakh et al., 2007; Ramamurthy and Harikrishnan, 2006; González-Corrochano et al., 2016) confirmed the existence of a strong positive linear correlation between the values of compressive S and ρ_{rd} .

The plots obtained for density confirm this direct relationship with S . Specifically, the response surface plots (Fig. 8a) and b) show that density reaches its highest values when the percentage of GCS or SCS is high and the CD content is 0%. Conversely, it decreases when the percentage of GCS or SCS decreases and CD content falls within the intermediate range. For example, in the case of slate cutting sludge, the lowest density values occur when CD content is intermediate and the SCS content ranges from 30 to 60% SCS with AWS between 40 and 65%. The effect plots show a similar trend for both types of cutting residues, confirming that the lowest density values are observed at CD levels close to the centroid (1.5%). Thus, decreasing the cork dust content increases density. Similarly, increasing the proportion of GCS/SCS and AWS raises density, while decreasing it initially lowers density and then causes a slight increase, though to a lesser extent.

Fig. 9a) and b) show the response surface plots of the BI for the GCS and SCS formulations. This parameter reaches its highest values in the red-coloured area and decreases thereafter, with the lowest values corresponding to mixtures with high GCS/SCS and low CD content. For example, in the case of LWAs made with slate cutting sludge, the highest BI values are observed at intermediate cork dust levels ($\approx 1.5\%$), with 15–50% SCS and 45–85% AWS (Fig. 9b). Furthermore, a clear inverse relationship between S and BI is evident. In fact, some mixtures,

specifically samples 6 and 11 for GCS and 6 for SCS (Table 7) show particularly high resistance values and exhibit negative expansion indices. The effects plots further reinforce this trend, displaying a pattern practically opposite to that of resistance: expansion is greatest at intermediate values of the organic residue, decreasing as the proportion of CD deviates from the centroid (1.5%). Additionally, as the content of GCS, SCS and AWS increases, the expansion effect decreases.

The combined analysis of the three properties (S , ρ_{rd} and BI) highlights the strong dependence of these parameters with the proportion of pore-forming agent in the mixture. Minimum values of density and strength, and maximum values of BI are reached at approximately 1.5% cork dust. In other words, volumetric expansion initially increases with CD content for samples with less than 1.5% residue. However, beyond the threshold, higher levels of organic residue result in lower volumetric expansion, meaning that expansion is inhibited as the proportion of organic matter increases in the mixture. The outcome consistent with findings from other studies, which have shown that only small amounts of pore-forming agents promote the expansion of aggregates. The contraction observed at higher organic residue contents may be related to an imbalance in the chemical composition and microstructure required for the expansion phenomenon (Moreno-Maroto and Alonso-Azcárate, 2017; Romero et al., 2024). It is important to note that for swelling to occur, sufficient liquid phases must form with adequate viscosity to trap the gases related during firing. The combustion of an excess of organic residue may create too many voids in the ceramic matrix, which are then filled by the liquid phase generated by metallic oxides present in the material (Moreno-Maroto et al., 2019). Ultimately, this leads to a densification of the material as a result of reduced porosity, which in turn causes contraction and consequently increases the mechanical strength of the aggregate.

The response surface plots of water absorption (Fig. 10a) and b) show that the highest WA_{24} values are obtained for mixtures with around 2.5% CD, around 30% cutting sludge and 65% AWS. Specifically, for LWAs made with granite cutting sludge, the GCS content ranges between 15 and 55% and AWS between 42 and 85%, while for those made with slate cutting sludge, SCS content is roughly between 20 and 40% and AWS between 57 and 80%. On the other hand, the lowest values of this parameter are obtained for mixtures with little organic additive. The effect plot shows that water absorption decreases with decreasing CD ratio, or with increasing GCS/SCS or AWS ratio. In contrast, WA_{24} is higher at values close to the centroid, increasing

Fig. 7. Response surface plots and effect plots for crushing strength: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

slightly with slightly decreasing proportion of cutting slurry or AWS ratio, which is in agreement with the picture given by the response surface plots.

The model that relates the mixture composition to the sintering

temperature and to the optimum water content for the manufacture of the mixtures has also been determined. In all cases, it has been found that the most suitable model is quadratic (Table 12), although non-significant terms have been eliminated, which improves the fit (except

Fig. 8. Response surface plots and effect plots for oven-dry density: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

for the temperature in SCS, which is linear, but in which significant quadratic terms have been added). In addition, it has been necessary to transform the W_{op} variable using the inverse of the square root. The estimated coefficients are shown in Table 13. The diagnosis carried out can be found in the supplementary material.

Fig. 11 shows the response surface plots for temperature, both for GCS (Fig. 11a) and SCS (Fig. 11b). These figures show that lower temperatures are required for mixtures without GCS or SCS and with 3 % CD, while higher temperatures are needed for mixtures with more GCS or SCS and less CD. This is consistent with the “black core” phenomenon

Fig. 9. Response surface plots and effect plots for bloating index: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

and the results discussed in Section 3.2. The exothermic nature of the reaction, combined with the incomplete oxidation of the organic residue, generates an oxygen-deficient atmosphere. This condition facilitates the reduction of Fe_2O_3 present in the waste to FeO , producing a fluid phase with suitable viscosity for gas entrapment. This enables the

expansion phenomenon to occur at lower temperatures (Cobo-Ceacero et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2019; Moreno-Maroto et al., 2019; Park et al., 2005)

The response surface plots for the Wop variable (Fig. 12a) and 12b)) are similar to each other and show that the highest Wop values are found

Fig. 10. Response surface plots and effect plots for water absorption: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

for higher cork and GCS or SCS ratios, being lower for intermediate values of GCS or SCS (between 15 and 50 %) and no cork.

3.4.1. Comparison between LWAS obtained according to GCS and SCS

Fig. 6 shows a similar behaviour between the LWAs obtained with

GCS and SCS, so it has been checked if this happens with all the technological properties, so that it is possible to use any of them indistinctly. For this purpose, the 4 technological properties have been considered and it has been analysed whether it is necessary to use a different model for GCS and SCS or whether a single model can be considered for both.

Table 12

Regression models for temperature and W_{op} for GCS-CD and SCS-CD mix: sequential p-values for comparison of models.

Models	GCS-CD mix		SCS-CD mix	
	Temp	$1/\sqrt{(W_{op})}$	Temp	$1/\sqrt{(W_{op})}$
Linear	0.0001	0.0428	0.0001	0.0055
Quadratic	0.0236	0.0001	0.1709	0.0012
Special Cubic	0.6760	0.0870	0.2917	0.8310
Cubic	0.0724	0.5946	0.3275	0.7212

Table 13

Coefficients of the regression models for temperature and W_{op} for GCS-CD and SCS-CD mix.

	GCS-CD mix		SCS mix	
	Temp	$1/\sqrt{(W_{op})}$	Temp	$1/\sqrt{(W_{op})}$
CS ^a	1229.1189	0.134997	1235.3391	0.159861
CD	33269.1890	-0.203573	32990.2182	-0.427794
AWS	1194.0680	0.178184	1196.2634	0.178256
CD:CS ^a	-32988.6396		-33618.3311	
AWS:CS ^a	-21.9984	0.107268		0.055045
CD:AWS	-34199.1342		-34108.5271	0.420843
R squared	0.9546	0.9536	0.9593	0.9588
Predicted R squared	0.8831	0.9381	0.8995	0.9118
p-value	0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

^a CS: granite or slate cutting sludge.

This can be done statistically by means of a contrast comparing a more general model (different for GCS and SCS) with a more reduced model (the same for both sludges). The results are shown in Table 14, where it can be seen that all p-values are very large, so that the reduced model cannot be rejected against the more general model.

In other words, for a given mix with GCS, the aggregate obtained will have technological properties that are not significantly different from those that would be obtained for an aggregate with SCS. This opens the door to being able to use both wastes interchangeably and even mixed together in different proportions to manufacture LWAs depending on the availability of each of them at any given time.

3.5. Optimization Y validation

Based on the models proposed for each technological property in Table 10, a numerical optimisation process has been carried out to determine the mixtures with maximum values for the BI , WA_{24} and S parameters and minimum values for ρ_{rd} . Real images of the optimum aggregates manufactured are included in Figs. 7–10, using the values estimated by the models as initial values of temperature and W_{op} . Table 15 includes the values of the parameters obtained experimentally, as well as those estimated from the different models.

• Optimum strength (S)

In the case of S (Op-1), the optimal formulations of the models (70GCS+0CD+30AWS and 80GCS+0CD+20AWS) had already been fabricated when proposed by the design of experiments. In this case, the experimentally obtained values are slightly higher than the estimated ones, namely 2.9 % for GCS and 10.8 % for SCS, although samples such as 11-GCS-CD present an S in the order of those estimated by the model (23.27 MPa). In this case, the optimal formulations are not lightweight aggregates due to their particle density values (2.35 y 2.16 > 2 g/cm³). However, formulations 6-SCS-CD (40 % SCS + 0 % CD + 60 % AWS), which is a lightweight aggregate (1.53 g/cm³), exhibits a compressive strength of 9.5 MPa, exceeding the minimum threshold of 7.5 MPa established by Liu et al. (2018) for use in civil engineering applications and is in the range reported by other authors for LWAs made from

washing aggregate sludge and fly ash (8.29 MPa), washing aggregate sludge and ground granulated blast furnace slag (10 MPa) or solid mining waste (11.51 MPa) (González Corrochano et al., 2009; Ozkan et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2023).

• Optimum bloating index (BI)

As for the BI (Op-2) for the case of GSC, the optimum of the model is obtained for the formulation 21GCS+1.7CD+77.3AWS (Table 15). In this case the estimated value is very close to the experimental one, 39.62 versus 38.96 % and of the order of that obtained in other samples previously tested such as 4-GCS-CD (37.68 %) and 7-GSC-CD (41.05 %) (Table 7). The same response is observed for the optimal formulation with the slate (32.1SCS+1.8CD+66.1AWS) with estimated and experimental values of 38.95 and 37.89 %, respectively. Samples 4-GCS-CD and 7-GSC-CD exhibit low compressive strength values (≈ 1.5 MPa), which makes them unsuitable for civil engineering applications. However, they show high water absorption values (23.3 % and 39.4 %, respectively), associated with their open porosity values (15.9 % and 25.3 %), making them suitable for use in gardening, horticulture and green roof applications. The optimal BI obtained are in the order of the maximum value reported by Jaha et al. (2024) for LWAs manufactured from palygorskite-rich sediment and phosphate sludge (38.5 %) and much lower than the maximum of 128 % achieved in the manufacture of LWAs using the organic fraction of recycled alkaline batteries (Romero et al., 2024).

• Optimum water absorption (WA_{24})

The water absorption model allows us to predict an optimum for the composition 33.5GCS-2.1CD-64.4AWS (Op-3; Table 15), for the case of granite sludge. The value estimated by the model is higher than that obtained experimentally (32.63 % as opposed to 25.27 %), although lower than two of the formulations obtained in the design of experiments, 7-GCS-CC and 10-GCS-CD, which reach 39.4 % and 34.9 %, respectively. In the case of the optimum with slate (30.5SCS+2.2CD+67.3AWS), the difference between the experimental and estimated values is minimised (31.31 as opposed to 33.78 %). Despite the fact that for water absorption the model does not fit as well as would be desirable in the case of granite sludge, in general it can be said that the proposed statistical models establish synergies between the components of the mixtures that allow the values of the technological properties studied to be predicted as a function of the composition of the formulation, which would not have been possible if the ME-DOE had not been used.

The high WA_{24} values obtained for the optimum values may lead to the conclusion that they cannot be used in construction or civil engineering. However, structural-grade lightweight aggregates can have WA_{24} values between 5 % and 25 %, and may even exceed 25 % or reach up to 34 % (Expanded Shale, Clay and Slate Institute [ESCSI], s.f.), provided they have an adequate S value. In this work, some formulations have been obtained that meet these characteristics (3-GCS-CD: 5.5 MPa-21.1 %; 3-SCS-CD: 5.3 MPa-21.9 %) and which may be of interest for application in lightweight concrete. Although high absorption values have been obtained in this study for some of the formulations (34.9 or 39.4 %), they are considerably lower than those obtained by da Silva Neto et al. (2025), who obtained a maximum value of 58.39 % for mixtures of waste rich in aluminosilicate and carbonate in kaolinitic clay.

The high internal water absorption of lightweight aggregates, far from being a problem, is key to the internal curing of concrete. This process allows the water absorbed within the aggregate to migrate to the capillary pores of the cement paste as it dehydrates, facilitating more complete hydration of the cement, resulting in a denser and less permeable microstructure that improves the long-term durability of the concrete and reduces its dependence on external curing (ESCSI, s.f.). However, very high moisture content in LWAs prior to mixing has been

a)

b)

Fig. 11. Response surface plots and effect plots for crushing temperature: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

associated with a reduction in the mechanical strength of concrete (Domagała and Bryła, 2021), so it is necessary to optimize the hydration of LWAs to avoid introducing excess water.

Existing regulations, such as the UNE-EN 13055-1, 2003 standard and the Spanish Structural Code (Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y

Agenda Urbana, 2021), recognise the unique nature of LWAs. Although they require the determination and declaration of the absorption rate, they take a performance-based approach rather than imposing rigid and universal absorption limits, allowing flexibility depending on the end use.

a)

b)

Fig. 12. Response surface plots and effect plots for Wop: a) GCS; b) SCS. Effect plots: x_1 = GCS or SCS; x_2 = CD; x_3 = AWS.

• Optimum oven-dry density (ρ_{rd})

For Op-4, which has been obtained by optimising the model proposed for oven-dry density, in the case of the mixture with granite

cutting sludge (26.3 GCS+1.8 CD+71.9 AWS) the experimental and estimated values coincide, 0.65 g/cm³ (Table 15). Furthermore, the estimated value is close to the values obtained experimentally in this work, such as those of samples 4-GCS-CD and 7-GCS-DC (0.67 and 0.62

Table 14
Comparison of models for both sludges.

Property	F statistic	p-value
Log(S)	0.3631	0.8903
BI	1.0012	0.4621
(WA ₂₄) ^{0.5}	0.3146	0.9187
1/(ρ _{rd}) ^{0.5}	1.1372	0.3912

g/cm³), respectively (Table 7). In the case of the shale mud, the optimum obtained for density (44.7SCS+1.9CD+53.4AWS) provides values for the experimental and estimated parameters that practically coincide (0.63 and 0.62 g/cm³, respectively). The results obtained indicate that the proposed model has a high level of prediction for this property. The values for the optimums are of the same order as those obtained in other studies involving solid mining waste, sand sludge and zeolite rocks or mixtures of granite waste and clay, 0.64, 0.70 and 0.65 respectively (Tang et al., 2023; Volland and Brötz, 2015; Soltan et al., 2016). In this case, due to the low mechanical strength of the aggregates obtained, their potential applications could also be related to gardening, horticulture and green roofs.

3.6. Mineral formation during sintering

A study of the microstructure of the optimum S and BI formulations for both types of ornamental sludge have been carried out by scanning optical microscopy (SEM). Figs. 13 and 14 show the images obtained. In the particular case of S, it can be observed for both types of sludge that the pore size is small and there is no marked difference between the pores in the shell and core of the aggregate (Fig. 13a, b), 14a) and 14b)). However, in the images corresponding to the BI optimum, aggregates in which the 'black core' effect occurs (Fig. 13c, d), 14c) and 14d)), there is a notable difference in the porosity of both areas, showing differences between the part of the shell with small pore size and the part of the core that is light and very porous, with much larger pore sizes. This observation suggests that the core part of the aggregate swelled due to viscous behaviour and that the shell part exhibited elastic behaviour (Wie et al., 2020a).

Table 16 shows the results of Rietveld's refinement of the optimum characterised by microscopy. As expected, the amorphous phase is the most important with values between 65.7 and 67.8 %. As for the crystalline phases, the generation of three new phases is observed: spinel which appears in all specimens, mullite which is formed exclusively in the BI optimum and hematite. The appearance of mullite exclusively in the BI optimum suggests that the formation of this phase could be related to the presence of organic residue, since this component is not

Table 15
Comparison between the experimental values of the selected technological properties with the optimal value obtained from the proposed statistical model.

GSC													
	Composition	T, °C		BI, %		WA ₂₄ , %		ρ _{rd} g/cm ³		S, MPa		W _{op} , %	
		Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est
Optimum	Composition	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est
Op-1: Optimun S (Model log S)	70GCS+0CD+30AWS	1215.0	1214.0	-10.21	-11.41	0.99	0.80	2.35	3.77	23.95	23.28	32.5	34.4
Op-2: Optimun BI	21GCS+1.7CD+77.3AWS	1195.0	1176.0	38.96	39.63	25.80	31.34	0.66	0.67	1.60	1.48	29.9	30.9
Op-3: Optimun WA ₂₄ (Model √WA ₂₄)	33.5GCS+2.1CD+64.4AWS	1205.0	1180.1	36.52	37.47	25.27	32.63	0.67	0.68	1.99	1.53	30,1	31.3
Op-4: Optimun ρ _{rd} (Model 1/√ρ _{rd})	26.3GCS+1.8CD+71.9AWS	1185.0	1177.7	36.57	39.36	32.91	31.99	0.65	0.65	1.64	1.45	30.7	30.8
SCS													
Optimum	Composition	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est	Exp.	Est
Op-1: Optimun S (Model log S)	80SCS+0CD+20AWS	1225.0	1226.9	-10.14	-10.50	0.26	0.74	2.16	2.40	19.83	17.90	29,1	33.7
Op-2: Optimun BI	32.2SCS+1.8CD+66AWS	1200.0	1185.0	37.89	38.95	22.15	34.22	0.63	0.63	1.49	1.32	30,9	31.5
Op-3: Optimun WA ₂₄ (Model √WA ₂₄)	30.5SCS+2.2CD+67.3AWS	1180.0	1177.3	34.26	37.60	31.31	33.78	0.69	0.63	1.97	1.46	31.4	31.9
Op-4: Optimun ρ _{rd} (Model 1/√ρ _{rd})	44.7SCS+1.9CD+53.4AWS	1200.0	1189.6	35.80	38.44	24.10	33.38	0.63	0.62	1.30	1.20	30.8	32.3

present in the compositions of the S optimum. On the other hand, the low thermal conductivity of mullite, together with the internal porosity, may contribute to increase the thermal insulation capacity of these aggregates, a very interesting property in many of the applications for which this type of material is intended. On the other hand, if the crystalline phases of the new materials obtained are compared with those of the original waste (Table 5), it can be seen that the illite, muscovite, chlorite and alkali feldspar phases have disappeared. It is expected that they have contributed to the formation of the mullite and spinel neophases.

3.7. LWAs for growing substrate

Finally, the capacity of the aggregates manufactured in this research to be used as substrates for cultivation has been explored. For this purpose, the two optimum formulations for water absorption (Op-3) were selected and an extraction of soluble elements was carried out in accordance with the UNE-EN 13650, 2002 standard. Table 17 shows the results of the test, as well as the limits set by Real Decreto 865/2020 on growing media.

As can be seen in both cases, the values obtained for all metals are well below the limits established by legislation for use as a 'class A' growing substrate, so that they can be used in edible horticultural crops. Furthermore, these aggregates present high total porosity values, 74.2 and 73.5 % for the granite and slate specimens respectively, of the order obtained by Volland and Brötz (2015) in LWAs produced from sand sludge and zeolite rocks (P_T 60–70 %) and close to the value of 86 % declared by the manufacturer of the commercial product Arlita Agri (ARLITA, s.f.) with applications in green roofs, landscaping, floriculture, gardening, horticulture and hydroponics.

3.8. Environmental assessment

The environmental impact has been assessed using the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) methodology, which measures the environmental impact caused using the GWP (Global Warming Potential) category. One ton of ALAs has been taken as the reference unit and the system has been limited from the extraction of raw materials to the manufacture of aggregates. Therefore, the study was carried out using a cradle-to-gate approach, not taking into account the end useful life of the products, as the performance and maintenance requirements of the products are difficult to assess comprehensively (Frischknecht and Rebitzer, 2005). With regard to the distance travelled, it should be clarified that in all scenarios, transport is assumed to be by EURO6 trucks from the source to the treatment plant, considering a generic distance of 50 km (one way only).

Fig. 13. SEM image of the cross section of optimal GSC aggregates. Op-1: a) core; b) shell. Op-2: c) core; d) shell.

Lightweight aggregate obtained exclusively from expanded clay (EC) has been used as a reference. Fig. 15 compares new materials manufactured from waste with traditional clay aggregate in terms of their contribution to climate change, from the extraction of raw materials to their manufacture.

The reference material (EC), lightweight aggregate made from pure clay, has a value of 122 kg CO₂ eq/t, mainly due to direct emissions from the decarbonisation of CaCO₃, the burning of organic matter present in the clay, and indirect emissions such as the energy required for clay extraction, grinding/preparation and, above all, high-temperature sintering in a kiln (1200 °C), which involves high consumption of fossil fuels or electricity generated from them (Uceda-Rodríguez et al., 2022).

The compositions of lightweight aggregates made from granite sludge (GCS) show a drastic reduction in GWP compared to conventional expanded clay.

The Op-1 (GCS) composition is by far the most advantageous from a

GWP point of view, with only 26.74 kg CO₂ eq/ton. The other compositions with GCS (Op-2, Op-3, Op-4) also exhibit considerably low GWP (between 49.9 and 53.3 kg CO₂ eq/ton). This notable reduction is attributed to the use of a waste product as the main raw material, which minimises the need for extraction of virgin resources, as well as to the characteristics of the manufacturing process of these mixtures, which require less energy as they are already ground waste that does not need prior treatment and incorporate organic waste that reduces the firing temperature, as well as emitting fewer direct greenhouse gases.

The low presence of carbonates and organic matter (LOI GCS 0.6 %; Table 5) and its mainly silicate composition do not release direct CO₂ when sintered in the temperature range 1185-1215 °C (Table 15). Its direct contribution to CO₂ emissions is minimal. In this group, the impact remains extremely low in all formulations (~50 kg CO₂ eq/t), even when AWS is the majority component.

The impacts of aggregates manufactured with GCS are so low and

Fig. 14. SEM image of the cross section of optimal SSC aggregates. Op-1: a) core; b) shell. Op-2: c) core; d) shell.

Table 16
Crystalline phases (%) observed in optimal LWAs formulations by Rietveld refinement.

	Quartz	Spinel	Mullita	Plagioclase	Hematite	Amorphous
Op1-GSC	19.9	1.5		11.6	1.4	65.7
Op1-SCS	25.4	6.1			0.7	67.8
Op2-GSC	21.1	3.4	5.3	3.3		66.9
Op2-SCS	21.8	6.7	4.1		0.1	67.3

close to each other, that small variations may be the result of slight changes in sintering efficiency, the accuracy of the LCA modelling or small fluctuations in the actual process conditions in the laboratory, rather than a linear effect of the addition of AWS or DC. Its role is rather that of an inert component of the matrix or a composition adjuster that helps to achieve the desired properties of the material (Saberian et al., 2021). Although DC does not reduce the global warming impact in this context, its incorporation as a secondary raw material represents an advantage, not only because of its potential role in the process (Cobo-Ceacero et al., 2023), but also from the perspective of integrated waste management and the circular economy, as it approaches 100 % recycling efficiency after its useful life (Romero et al., 2025).

Aggregates manufactured with SCS have a higher GWP than those manufactured with GCS. The environmental impacts associated with the Op-1 (SCS) composition (77.10 kg CO₂ eq/t) are 65 % higher than Op-1 (GCS). SCS has an LOI of 3.2 %, much higher than GCS (Table 5). The

Table 17

Result of the aqua regia soluble elements extraction test.

	¹¹¹ Cd	⁶³ Cu	⁶⁰ Ni	²⁰⁵ Pb	⁶⁶ Zn	²⁰¹ Hg	⁵² Cr
Op3-GSC	0.019	3.265	2.949	n.d.	158.610	n.d.	n.d.
Op3-SCS	0.018	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.014
Class A	0.700	70.000	25.000	45.000	200.000	0.400	70.000
Class B ^a	2.000	300.000	90.000	150.000	500.000	1.500	250.000

^a Class B products may not be used on edible horticultural crops.

Fig. 15. Comparison of the environmental impacts generated between the reference material (k) and the optimal LWAs obtained in this research (Op-1; Op-2; Op-3; Op-4) for GCS and SCS.

decomposition of clay minerals or traces of carbonates, or organic matter that release CO₂, causes direct emissions that increase the GWP. In addition, the rich composition of SCS in laminar minerals (micas, chlorites) may require much more thermal energy than the sintering of materials with simpler compositions or that melt at lower temperatures. Op-1 aggregate (SCS) sintered at the highest temperature (1225 °C; Table 15).

The addition of an agent that provides internal energy (such as cork) reduces the external energy consumption of the furnace, which is why Op-2, Op-3 and Op-4 have lower sintering temperatures when cork is incorporated into their formulation (1180–1200 °C; Table 15). The presence of small amounts of DC is the critical differentiating factor in SCS aggregates. Cork acts as an internal fuel or co-fuel. When burned during sintering, it releases a large amount of heat. Less external energy means fewer indirect CO₂ emissions associated with the generation of that energy.

For its part, the addition of AWS to aggregates manufactured with SCS not only adjusts the composition, but is also an essential component that allows the system to function efficiently (particularly with cork) by mitigating the inherent challenges of SCS and helping to achieve the desired sintering and lightness at a given temperature, showing a GWP increase of up to 28 % compared to Op-1 (SCS) in the case of aggregate Op-4 (SCS) but still much lower than k (108 kg CO₂ eq compared to 122.97 kg CO₂ eq).

4. Conclusions

This research focuses on developing a method for producing artificial lightweight aggregates (LWAs) using only waste materials. An innovative combination of aggregate washing sludge, granite and slate cutting sludge, and organic cork dust was employed. The study aimed not only to demonstrate the feasibility of producing these materials without using natural raw resources but also to ensure that the resulting LWAs would be suitable for applications in construction, green roofs, horticulture, hydroponics, and landscaping.

The main conclusions of the study reveal key findings regarding composition and processing. It was found that the high proportion of

phyllosilicates in the aggregate washing sludge is essential, as it provides the necessary plasticity to the mixtures, compensating for less plastic components. The Mixture Experiments–Design of Experiments (ME–DOE) methodology proved highly effective, significantly reducing the number of formulations to be tested. Additionally, the incorporation of a small amount of organic cork powder (0–3 %; centroid ≈1.5 % by weight) lowers the sintering temperature and, due to its calorific value, reduces the dependence on fossil fuels, thereby decreasing greenhouse gas emissions.

In terms of performance and applicability, the results were highly promising. Nearly all LWA formulations obtained (10 out of 13) meet the criteria of the UNE-EN 13055-1:2003 standard, qualifying them as lightweight aggregates. The technological properties of the resulting LWAs are comparable to those of commercial products such as Arlita, Laterlite, Puma, or NexClay. In fact, in terms of mechanical strength, some formulations outperformed commercial options, offering additional advantages for use in construction and civil engineering (e.g., 6-SCS-CD; 9.5 MPa). Furthermore, the study showed that the type of ornamental stone sludge (granite or slate) does not significantly affect the properties of the LWAs, allowing for flexible use depending on availability.

Accurate statistical models were developed to optimize the manufacturing process, enabling the estimation of both the sintering temperature and the required water content, as well as to predict the technological properties of the LWAs based on the initial mix composition. In all cases, the models were statistically significant (p-value <0.05) with high coefficients of determination (R²: 0.80–0.94).

Finally, this study highlights the environmental benefits of manufactured materials compared to artificial aggregates obtained from clay. The GWP values achieved by the optimal LWAs show reductions of between 13 and 36 % for SCS and 56–78 % for GCS compared to the reference material. Therefore, the manufacture of LWA from the industrial waste used in this research could become an alternative for the production of sustainable materials with a lower environmental footprint by reducing the impact of traditional mining.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María Teresa Cotes-Palomino: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jacinto Alonso-Azcárate:** Supervision. **Antonio Conde-Sánchez:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Alejandro Dubbelman Vizcaino:** Resources, Investigation. **Ana B. López:** García, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Carmen Martínez-García:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Ana M. Martínez-Rodríguez:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ana Cecilia Revelo Rodríguez:** Resources, Investigation. **Francisco José Troyano Pérez:** Resources, Investigation. **Carlos Javier Cobo-Ceacero:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

Consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent to publish

Not applicable.

Data availability statement

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this manuscript.

Funding

“This work was supported by ‘INGEMATS Project - Ingeniería Circular aplicada a la obtención de materiales sostenibles a partir de residuos. Avanzando hacia la neutralidad climática’ (Grant number ProyExcel_00797). Andalusian Regional Government. Incentives for Excellence Research Projects, R + D + I Andalusian Plan, call 2021”.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: MT Cotes-Palomino reports financial support was provided by University of Jaen. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research was conducted as a part of the INGEMATS Project, ProyExcel_00797, “Ingeniería Circular aplicada a la obtención de materiales sostenibles a partir de residuos. Avanzando hacia la neutralidad climática”. Andalusian Regional Government. Incentives for Excellence Research Projects, R + D + I Andalusian Plan, call 2021. Thanks also to the Central Research Support Services of the University of Jaén (Spain), the University of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain) and the University of Málaga (Spain) for their services.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2025.122321>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Nomenclature

- LWAs: Lightweight aggregates
 ME-DOE: Mixture Experiments-Design of Experiments
 GCS: Granite cutting sludge
 SCS: Slate cutting sludge
 AWS: Aggregate washing sludge
 CD: Cork dust
 EC: Expanded clay
 LL: Atterberg liquid limit
 PL: Atterberg plastic limit
 PI: Atterberg plasticity index
 W_{opt} : Optimal water content for extrusion
 BI: Bloating Index
 WA_{24} : water absorption during 24h
 S: Single particle crushing strength
 ρ_{rd} : Oven-dry density
 ρ_b : Loose bulk density
 ρ_{rd} : Apparent density
 ρ_{solid} : Density of the solid phase of a LWA
 P_T : Total porosity
 P_O : Open porosity
 P_C : Closed porosity
 V_{PO} : Open porosity volume per specimen